

Information, Quantum Probability and Reflection/Refraction Part IV Particle Wave Duality

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In a number of notes (Parts I,II,III) we considered the problem of photons A moving in the positive x direction striking a medium at $x=0$ and reflecting B and refracting C. In (1) conservation of energy: $I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2$ ((1)), where $I(A)$ is intensity which has the form of energy * velocity i.e. a flux, is given. Thus $I(A)/c_1 = n_1 E$, $I(B)=n_2 E$ and $I(C)=n_3 E$, where E is constant energy of a photon and n_i are the number of photons. Conservation of energy/or photon is a conservation law in terms of “particles” and is furthermore a time averaged result. A single photon either reflects or refracts. In both cases conservation of particle number and energy exists and so one may wonder why one needs a time averaged “particle” type conservation equation in the first place. We argue that it demonstrates the role of flux in this problem - a role which differs from that of hydrodynamics in classical physics. ((1)) shows immediately that there is neither conservation of flux i.e. $I(A)$ values or momentum even in a steady state scenario (i.e. time averaged scenario) represented by ((1)). This is different from an incompressible liquid moving from a wide pipe to a narrow one. In such a case flux is conserved yet microscopic particles change velocity, momentum and energy.

As noted in Part I, one may write: $I(A)/c_1 - I(B)/c_1 = I(C)/c_2$, multiply by E (energy) and use $E=pc$. This yields a “kind” of momentum conservation equation, but not in terms of particle numbers (i.e. not in a particle picture). Rather $I(A)p$ is momentum multiplied by flux which is unusual.

((1)) is a conservation of particle number and energy, but does not include conservation of flux or momentum flux which one might expect in a steady state flow equation and which appears in classical fluid dynamics. As noted in Part I to obtain these additional conservation/balance equations one is forced to use square root probabilities i.e. $I(A)=AA$ with A representing a square root flux or dynamic probability. Using the idea of differences of squares, one may write: $A + B = C$ ((2a)) and $A^2 - B^2 = C^2$ ((2b)) and solve for B and C in terms of A . In other words a hydrodynamical approach applies to the square root probabilities A,B,C and not to $I(A)=AA$ etc.

Ultimately squaring, one obtains $I(A),I(B)$ and $I(C)$ showing that the square root probability or wave/dynamical probability represents balance and conservation. In ((2a)) and ((2b)) i.e. with square root probabilities one has dropped the view of particles and changed to a square root flux/ new dynamical probability picture together with its balances. This is in fact the wave picture because A,B,C are linked with $\exp(ip_1x),\exp(-ip_1x)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$ (which for photons are associated with the wave picture of the electric and magnetic fields). Thus even though there is particle wave duality, in terms of conservation waves (square root probabilities) yield particle conservation equations. For example, it is the wave picture which allows one to solve for B and C in terms of A . The wave picture may be associated with a steady state (time removed) equilibrium scenario in which dynamical (square root) probabilities add in space (not by time grouping) and it contains both conservation of probability and momentum probability while momentum (of the particles) may not be conserved in the particle picture as is the case for the reflection/refraction problem. Particle number/energy are also guaranteed.

Particle Wave Duality

Particle wave duality is an important feature of both photons and quantum particles with rest mass, but the two natures are often treated on the same footing i.e. some experiments show wave properties and others, particle. In other words we argue that a connection between the two is not given. For example, in Newtonian mechanics one may describe an object with a rest mass as a particle. There is no need to bring in a wave picture. So why should a wave picture exist in quantum mechanics (together with a particle one)? To attempt to answer this question we consider the problem of a beam of light moving in the positive x direction striking a medium and reflecting/refracting.

Reflection/Refraction of Light

A single photon striking a medium is a probabilistic situation in which there is a certain probability for the photon to reflect or refract. Energy is automatically conserved as is particle number, but not the momentum of the photon. The incident momentum is p_1 , the reflected $-p_1$ and the refracted p_2 . This problem may also be viewed as a steady state one with continuous beams of incident, reflected and refracted photons existing at the same time. In such a case, fluxes appear naturally in the problem. In classical mechanics, $p=mv$ or $p=mv/\sqrt{(1-vv/cc)}$ appears. Here one may think of flux as:

$$I(A)=AA = \text{number of photons } (n) * \text{energy} * \text{velocity } ((3))$$

We write $I(A)=AA$ to indicate that the flux must be positive. Thus $I(A)/c_1 = n_1 E$, but E is the same for incident, reflected and refracted photons. One may write a steady state or time averaged conservation of energy equations including the probabilistic unknowns $I(B)=BB$ and $I(C)=CC$ as in (1):

$$I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2 \quad ((4))$$

This is grouped in time, but as noted it represents a time averaged or steady state scenario and conservation of particle number and energy is already a given without ((4)). Thus it seems the purpose of ((4)) is to include the notion of flux (which appears in momentum and hydrodynamics).

((4)) is an equation which holds in a "particle" scenario. It includes two unknowns $I(B)$ and $I(C)$ if $I(A)$ is considered known, but does not allow for the solution of these as it stands.

A main point we wish to make is that in classical mechanics one has both particle conservation equations and flux conservations, the latter being associated with hydrodynamics. For example, one may have an incompressible fluid/gas moving through a wide pipe (cross sectional area A_1) transfer to a narrow pipe (A_2). One then equates flux:

$$A_1v_1 = A_2v_2 \quad ((5))$$

Thus ((5)) exists in a particle scenario. ((5)) shows that even though a single molecule changes its velocity v_1 to v_2 which means that its momentum and energy also changes (unlike the photon), but the aggregate momentum (i.e. flux) proportional to A_1v_1 does not change i.e. multiplying ((5)) by density $\times L$ where L is a fixed length yields mass. Thus for a fixed L , mass changes and v changes, but the product i.e. the momentum of the aggregate does not change, even though it does for a single molecule. ((5)) shows that there is conservation of flux, but there is no conservation of energy as: Pressure 1 - Pressure 2 = $-.5 \text{ density } v_1v_1 + .5 \text{ density } v_2v_2$ (2).

Equation ((4)) which represents conservation of energy/particle number at the same time shows that one does not have conservation of flux i.e.:

$$I(A) \text{ is not equal to } I(B)+I(C) \quad \text{and} \quad I(A)p_1 \text{ is not equal to } I(B)(-p_1) + I(C) p_2$$

Thus flux balances break down in the steady state picture of reflection/refraction in contrast to fluid/gas hydrodynamics. Ultimately one would like to have both particle conservation equations and hydrodynamical flux type equations somehow linked with flow. The reason for this is that if a steady state system exists, this is like an equilibrium and should be based on balance equations, but do not directly involve intensity/flux. Energy and particle number are automatically balanced because a photon remains intact and does not change its energy when reflecting or refracting. Thus energy/particle number is not the conservation or balance associated with steady state behaviour even though it is represented by an equation ((4)) displaying intensities. There should exist further balance equations, in fact at least two of them, as there are two unknowns $I(B)=BB$ and $I(C)=CC$ if $I(A)$ is known.

Even though this may not be achieved for $I(A)=AA$ etc, it holds for A i.e. the square root of flux. Thus a kind of square root dynamical probability appears. To see this mathematically, consider writing ((4)) as:

$$AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/ c_2 \quad ((6a))$$

One may multiply by E to obtain $AAp_1 - BBp_1 = CCp_2$ ((6b)). This is an unusual equation as AAp_1 is flux multiplied by p_1 . The difference of squares in ((6a)) implies that mathematically one may write:

$$A+B= C \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p_1A - p_1B = p_2C \quad ((7b))$$

((6a)) is a particle scenario, while ((7a)),((7b)) are the corresponding square root or wave picture. Thus the two pictures are specifically connected. ((7a)) has the appearance of conservation of a kind of probability and ((7b)) of momentum. In other words hydrodynamical behaviour, or balancing based on dynamical quantities, seems to hold at the wave or square root probability level.

One may note immediately that the probabilities in ((7a)) and ((7b)) are not classical because for $n_1 < n_2$, B is negative. Thus some positive probability of A is offset by the negative B to balance the reduced C positive probability (i.e. $C < A$). Similarly ((7b)) in this situation means that $p_1(A+|B|) = p_2 C$. $A > C$ so $A+|B| > C$, but $p_1 < p_2$. Thus the two balancing equations yield values for B and C in terms of A and are of physical importance.

We point out that time has completely disappeared from the picture in ((7a)), ((7b)) as has the notion of a particle. One is only interested in conservation associated with dynamical quantities i.e. with the flow although square roots of the actual fluxes A,B,C are used because conservation of dynamical quantities does not exist at the AA, BB, CC level.

We also note that the wave/ square root probability scenario is associated with conservation of dynamical quantities i.e. p and square-root flux and at the same time leads to associated particle number and energy conservation i.e. ((4)). Thus the wave/square root flux picture seems to be completely based on conservation at two different levels: the dynamical and the static i.e. particle and energy as quantities.

Particle with Rest Mass Scenario

The above arguments have been made for light moving in one dimension reflecting and refracting. What about a particle with rest mass? One may consider a particle with fixed momentum striking a potential and as in (3) consider asymptotic solutions of the Schrodinger equations as:

$$A \exp(ip_1 x) + B \exp(-ip_1 x) \text{ (at -infinite)} \quad \text{and} \quad C \exp(ip_1 x) \text{ (at infinite)} \quad ((8))$$

This suggests conservation of energy as only a single p_1 value is used. One may again consider two sets of equations, one related to the square root flux/wave probabilities and the other set to the momentum i.e.

$$A p_1 \exp(ip_1 x) - B p_1 \exp(-ip_1 x) \text{ (at -infinite)} \quad \text{and} \quad C p_1 \exp(ip_1 x) \text{ (infinite)} \quad ((9))$$

Again one sees that the reflected ray flux may reduce the incident ray's A (square root flux) to account for the reduced C. Multiplying the complex conjugate of ((8)) with ((9)) which at -infinite is again a difference of squares yields:

$$A^* A p_1 - p_1 B^* B \text{ (at -infinite)} \quad \text{and} \quad C^* C p_1 \text{ (at infinite)} \quad ((10))$$

At -infinite there is the mixed term proportional to $\cos(2p_1 x)$, but this is 0 on average. Thus one has: $A^* A = B^* B + C^* C$ which is equivalent to probability conservation i.e. exists at the level of particles. In other words, overall conservation of particles is still guaranteed although $A \exp(ip_1 x)$ and $B \exp(-ip_1 x)$ may interfere to achieve this.

The fundamental solution of such a problem, however, depends on the square root or wave probability. For example, for scattering from a three dimensional infinite potential for $r < r_0$, the wave function (wave square root) probability is 0 within $r < r_0$ and so $W(r)$ for $r > 0$ must become $W(r_0) = 0$. In other words there is continuity of the square root probability. (4) At first it may

appear as if only a single wave type equation is used i.e. $W(r)$ at $r=r_0$, but the momentum type equation is needed to deal with coefficients in $W(r)$ and ensure that there is overall particle conservation. Thus a wave solution of scattering off an infinite potential in three dimensions automatically includes conservation of particle number i.e. the wave approach is a built-in particle level conservation mechanism which introduces continuity of square root flux/wave probability and momentum flux $-i/2m (W^*d/dxW - Wd/dxW^*)$ to find actual balances in the physical problem. This is something that does not appear in classical mechanics. Thus wave mechanics not only solves for weights of reflected and transmitted particles (and phase shifts), but guarantees conservation of particles at the particle level even though interference occurs at the wave level for this to occur.

One may note that in the case of the reflection/refraction of light two different speeds c_1 and c_2 appear. This is due to the two media n_1 and n_2 which may be likened to two constant potentials V_1 and V_2 in quantum particle with rest mass scenario. If the interface is at $x=0$ one may solve this problem and energy is conserved then one may solve this problem in an analogous manner.

Conclusion

In Parts I,II and III we discussed the problem of light moving in the positive x direction reflecting/refracting at $x=0$ from a medium. Here we attempt to clarify some ideas linked to the particle/ wave=square root flux duality. We argued in Part III that conservation of photon number and energy are automatically given for a photon (regardless whether it reflects or refracts) so why write a flux/intensity equation: $I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2$ ((M)) where $I(g)=gg$ because I is positive? Intensity/flux $I(A)$ is of the form number of photons*energy*velocity, thus dividing by c_1,c_2 yields energy and particle conservation equations. These are applied to a time averaged or steady state picture. The latter, however, removes time and is a kind of equilibrium or hydrodynamical situation. In such a case, it should be associated with some kind of balance. Energy/particle number balance is a given and ((M)) shows that there is neither flux or momentum flux conservation. Thus there should be two other balance equations (because there are two unknowns $I(B),I(C)$ if $I(A)$ is known). Furthermore these two balance equations should somehow confirm conservation of energy/particle i.e. yield ((M)).

Using the idea of differences of squares, one is forced to go to the level of square roots of fluxes i.e. A instead of $I(A)=AA$ to obtain the two needed balance equations, one for square root flux or wavefunction i.e. wave dynamical probability, and the other for momentum. The product of the two yields the particle conservation equation ((M)). Thus the square root picture yields balances not seen in the particle realm (needed to solve the physical problem i.e. find B and C in terms of A) as well as guaranteeing conservation of numbers and energy in the particle view. In other words, the wave picture seems to be “all about” balance and conservation.

References

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